

STOPP READINESS TOOLS AND RESOURCES

PROBLEM ENCOUNTERED AND OBJECTIVE

The transition towards sustainable packaging, recycling, and reusing practices is often hindered by a lack of accessible, structured, and tailored information. Many individuals and organisations struggle to identify the right strategies and best practices suited to their level of knowledge. The Readiness Tools & Resources repository aims to bridge this gap by providing a comprehensive collection of training and communication materials. These resources, structured into Rookie, Player, and Expert levels, support users in gaining the necessary knowledge to implement circular and sustainable solutions effectively.

MAIN RESULTS / OUTCOMES

The repository offers a wide range of materials, including infographics, reports, guides, and case studies, designed to enhance understanding and application of sustainable packaging, recycling, and reusing practices. By catering to different expertise levels, it ensures that users can progress at their own pace, from basic concepts to advanced strategies. These resources facilitate informed decision-making, improve industry practices, and contribute to the broader adoption of circular economy principles. The structured learning approach enables businesses, policymakers, and individuals to implement practical and future-fit sustainability solutions.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

To make the most of the Readiness Tools & Resources, users should start by assessing their current knowledge level—Rookie, Player, or Expert—and select materials accordingly. Beginners can begin with introductory guides to build a strong foundation, while more experienced users can explore case studies and strategic insights to refine their approach. Organisations should integrate these resources into training programmes and decision-making processes to enhance sustainability initiatives. Regular engagement with updated materials will ensure continuous learning and adaptation to evolving best practices in sustainable packaging, recycling, and reuse.

Further information

Link to Readiness tools & resources: <https://stopp-project.eu/readiness-tools-resources/>

About this abstract

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STOPP is a Horizon Europe project aiming to transform food plastic packaging through the “5 Rs”: Refuse, Reduce, Redesign, Reuse, and Recycle. Aligned with the EU’s Packaging Directive, it develops training materials and strategies to promote circular economy solutions. Engaging stakeholders, STOPP advances recycling, reusable packaging, and consumer awareness for sustainable food packaging.

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